

The match between social entrepreneurship and sustainable development : The région of SOUSS MASSA in Morocco as Model

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Abstract

Our research analysis the relationship between, social entrepreneurship and sustainable development, we will try to present an inventory corresponding to the practices implemented by agricultural cooperatives operating in the SOUSS MASSA region in Morocco.

Generally, sustainable development is based on the activity of economic actors and the presence of social entrepreneurship in the implementation of the challenges of the sustainable development model. In this research work, we will present in the first axis, the monograph of the SOUSS MASSA region in Morocco, in order to have an idea of the sectors of activity of the region. In the second axis, the role of social enterprises, particularly cooperatives in economic development, and finally the relationship between sustainable development and social entrepreneurship

Keywords : social entrepreneurship, sustainable development, cooperatives

INTRODUCTION

Generally, the level of development in developing countries gives rise to the appearance of social entrepreneurship as a solution to the socio-economic imbalances marked by these countries. At this level, to emphasize this subject, we must recall the social and solidarity economy, which defines several fundamental actors making it possible to resolve the socio-economic gaps of countries. Generally, the best-known legal forms of the social and solidarity economy are associations, cooperatives and mutual societies.

The appearance of the foundations of social entrepreneurship and its effects in Morocco like a number of underdeveloped countries is mainly caused by the principle of solidarity. Initially, social entrepreneurship in Morocco is characterized by the role played by the INDH through financial incentives and assistance programs for the benefit of project holders, particularly young people and women in rural areas. And secondly, Moroccan culture has allowed the emergence of a new development model which values groups, not individuals, but also the tax regime adopted in Morocco which excludes participatory groups from taxes.

Social entrepreneurship in Morocco has marked the presence of a category of young Moroccans graduated from different local or foreign business or engineering schools, as well as young students enrolled in entrepreneurship awareness clubs and sponsored by international institutions, a new conception of social entrepreneurship centered on the person at the origin of the initiative is gaining space. This concept “imported” from Anglo-Saxon countries has given rise to some social enterprise projects whose financial viability and social impact must be tested over time and also in reality.

In our research work we are interested in studying the impact of social entrepreneurship on sustainable development. The reflection we are carrying out challenges us on the question of convergence or the opposite of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development : “is there a relationship between sustainable development and social entrepreneurship, if so, how? »

The objective of this research work is the treatment of some methodological and analytical tools through the exploitation of the data collected through our questionnaire. These tools will constitute a technical guide for analyzing and interpreting the results.

The analysis of the relationship between sustainable development and social entrepreneurship involves the presentation of the monograph of the region in order to identify strategic sectors of the region. In our research work, we will try to combine aspects of social enterprises and the determinants of sustainable development.

It is with this in mind that this research proposes :

- *On the one hand, to identify and analyze the determinants of sustainable development and we intersect with social entrepreneurship.*
- *On the other hand, we seek the role of social enterprises*

I. . Monograph of the SOUSS MASSA region in Morocco

This region is one of the most dynamic regions in Morocco, it is characterized by its diversity in terms of the agri-food industry and local products.

1.1 Geographical and administrative presentation

This region is represented by 6 large cities: Agadir, Inzegane Ait Melloul , Chtouka Ait Baha , Tiznit, Taroudant and Tata, extends over an area equal to 51,642 km². It is located in west-central Morocco. Located in the south of Morocco, south of the High Atlas, it included the Souss plain, part of the anti Atlas and the region of Draa Tafilalt including the city of Ouarzazate.

In the map that follows we clearly see the position of the three areas studied in the Souss Massa region.

Figure 1: Provinces and prefectures of the Souss Massa region

Source : monograph of the Souss Massa region, 2015

The prefecture of Agadir Ida Outanane is the capital of the Souss Massa region. Since 1959, we spoke of the province of Agadir Ida Outanane until the year of 1994 that it became a prefecture. It is made up of one urban commune, and twelve rural communes, it also has six urban districts, two circles, five Caïdats. The Prefecture has an important human source, which

constitutes a real wealth. 79% of its population comes to the urban area, however 21% resides in the rural area. According to statistics provided by the High Commission for Planning and following the 2014 general population and housing census , the population of the Agadir Ida Outanane prefecture is estimated at 601,000 (HCP, 2014).

1.2 Productive sectors

1.2.1 Agriculture

On a national scale, the Souss Massa region is classified as the leading fruit and citrus growing region with an agricultural export of 44% from the Kingdom, a production of 21% and market gardening exports representing 80% of national exports. As for citrus fruits, regional production represents 48% of Morocco's production and its exports 62% of the country's total exports.

Agricultural activity in the Agadir region is of the subsistence type due to the scarcity of useful agricultural land, and the geographical nature of its surface area.

The irrigated areas consist, on the one hand, of the modern perimeter regrouped and equipped by the State, and on the other hand, of the private irrigated perimeters which fall under small and medium hydraulics mainly in mountainous areas.

➤ Agricultural production

The following table presents agricultural production in the three zones of the Agadir region:

Table 1: Agricultural production

Crops	Area (Ha)		Production (T)
Cereals		11450	211 100
Market gardening		2604	49,050
Citrus		64	835
Olivier		3165	4100
Almond		2411	84
Banana tree		525	3235
Fodder		850	15,950

Source: monograph of the Souss Massa region, 2015

➤ Breeding

The Agadir region is mainly known for goat breeding and beekeeping. In this sense, we find:

- ✓ Cattle: 41,600 Heads;
- ✓ Sheep: 128,100 Heads;
- ✓ Goats: 188,100 Heads.

Generally the number of cooperatives that operate in the agricultural sector, particularly in income-generating activities. The following table presents the existing cooperatives in the three zones of the Agadir region :

Table 2: Agricultural cooperatives in the Agadir region

Sectors	Number of cooperatives
Beekeeping	111
Argan	93
Fruits and vegetables	22
Dairy products	19
Other	102
Total	347

Source: Office for Development Cooperation ,2017

➤ Forests and Biodiversity

The Agadir region is also very well known for its wood production since it contains a forest area considered the largest in Morocco. Generally, the forests available to the Souss Massa region extend into the High Atlas and the Souss plain. The mountain is made up of natural forests of argan tree, thuja and holm oak, and the plain is made up of argan tree and eucalyptus-based dunes.

On the national and heritage level, in 1998, and on an area that spreads over two and a half million hectares, the Arganeraie was officially declared by UNESCO as the first biosphere reserve in the national scale.

1.2.2 Tourism

One of the most attractive sectors and the growth sector of the Moroccan economy, Tourism in the region of SOUSS MASSA, has a primordial role, since it contributes to the economic and social development at the level of the city and the National level. Generally, today, the development of the tourism sector and the turnover achieved at a global level,

organizations speak of the tourism industry which creates value, since it manages to increase foreign exchange earnings, which are at nearly 10 billion dirhams (36% at the level of Morocco), hence this industry presents a powerful lever for economic growth.

1.2.3 Industry, commerce and services

The third sector that creates value at the national level , the industrial, commercial and services sector.

➤ Industry

The industry contributes significantly to the economy of the SOUSS MASSA region. Indeed, in 2015, there were 313 units which represent 60% of the regional whole, and 4% in the composition of the fabric of the kingdom.

Its activity is based on the agri-food industry and especially on the valorization of fishery and agricultural wealth.

➤ Trade

The Soussi have a reputation as traders, from where they engage in trade and distribution. Given that it is the most important pillar of the SOUSS MASSA region, this sector participates in the creation of employment and wealth.

The commerce sector is an important lever of investment, and strongly drives the local economy by contributing to the organization and economic and social development of the region. The city of Inzegane monopolizes commercial activity, but Agadir remains a city characterized by the modernity of its commerce.

➤ Services

The services sector is a sector that creates jobs and income, it develops according to the economic and social situation of the region. The city of Agadir, which is the capital of the region, offers various services to citizens, investors and visitors.

➤ Craftsmanship

The craft sector plays an important socio-economic role in the Souss Massa region ; crafts are strongly linked to the economic driving sectors of this region.

The artisanal sector is a sector that generates jobs, and it has a great place in the life of the population of the region, thanks to its growth and dynamism.

The Souss Massa region has more than 17,000 artisans, the artisanal products of the region are diverse, original, and known nationally and even internationally. This richness comes from the fact that each province and prefecture has expertise which gives the items offered a different local aspect. We find the artisanal touch even in the building sector at the construction

level, and also in interior decoration, such as zellige belidi , tadllakt painting , plaster sculpture, and wood sculpture following the Amazigh tradition.

The main handicraft items from the Agadir region are:

- **Wood sculpture** : These products are essentially : doors, chests, moucharabia, ceiling columns, etc. they are made according to Amazigh tradition and designs ;
- **The building** : The work takes the form of ceilings, Zellige belidi, marble, Mosaic beams, or others...etc. ;
- **Thuya wood** : From this wood, craftsmen can make tables, desks, consoles, armchairs, and household items, etc.;
- **Ironwork** : ironwork items are : tables, display cases, doors, chairs, chandeliers, etc. ;
- **Traditional haute couture** : traditional haute couture products are djellabahs, caftans, takchitas, gandouras, etc. ;
- **Embroidery** : **Embroidery** products can be in the form of tablecloths, mattresses, clothes, curtains, placemats, etc. ;
- **Leather and suede** : Its items are mainly leather clothing and luggage.

According to the Development Office of La Coopération, the region has 88 artisanal cooperatives, ie 37 for Agadir Ida Outanane, 26 for Inzegane Ait Melloul and 25 for Chtouka Ait Baha. They include the following activities : sewing ; building ; the traditional bakery; the sale of handicrafts; the traditional zellige; woodwork ; building electricity; promotion and development of women; plumbing.

1.3 Social sectors

1.3.1 Primary, college and qualifying education

For any development of a country, the education sector is a vital sector. This is why the prefecture of Agadir Ida Outanane , the prefecture of Inzegane Ait Melloul and the province of Chtouka Ait Baha , have made great efforts to have infrastructures that meet the needs of the community, during the In the 2013-2014 school year, the indicators for this sector were as follows:

Table 3: Education sector indicators

Designations	Establishment	Roomsused	Number of students	Number of teachers
Primary education	302	3,298	146,338	4,658
Secondary college	79	1,436	73,542	2,670
Secondary qualifying	43	782	31,269	1,455
Total	424	5,516	251 149	8,783

Source : monograph of the Souss Massa region, 2015

The private education sector offers 224 establishments, this sector has a very important role, insofar as it welcomed, in the 2013/2014 school year, approximately 22,232 pupils, including 29,042 in primary education, 6,365 in college, and 3,793 in qualifying.

1.3.2 Higher Education

The region of Agadir, and more precisely the city of Agadir, is home to one of the great universities of Morocco, in this case the Ibn Zohr University. Its university map contains four regions, namely : the Souss Massa Region, Guelmim Oquadnoun , Laayoune Sakia El Hamra and Dakhla Oued Eddahab .

Zohr University is multidisciplinary, it contains Sciences, Economics, Law, Letters and Human and Social Sciences, Management and Commerce, Engineering and Technology, its host establishments are located in the city of Agadir, but there are other sites in Azrou Ait Melloul , Ouarzazate, Taroudannt, Guelmim , Lâayoune and Dakhla.

1.3.3 Health

The level of medical care available to the population of the region is an important factor that determines the well-being of the community. Supervision and medical infrastructure present the factors that determine the quality of care. Alongside the public sector, state investment, we find the private sector, which invests in order to fill the gap between public supply and the demand of the population of the Agadir region.

II. . Social enterprises in the Agadir region

The presentation of the elements of social entrepreneurship is a priority in this part, at this level, the main actors are associations and cooperatives. However, social entrepreneurship is a way of doing business that places economic efficiency at the service of the general interest. Indeed, it has a social or environmental goal by reinvesting the profits for the benefit of this purpose, whatever the legal status of the social enterprise: association, cooperative or mutual.

1. Associations

The association is determined as a group of voluntary people, who come together to found a common project and share a non-profit activity.

In order to have information concerning the associations at the local level, we moved respectively to the prefecture of Agadir Ida Outanane , the prefecture of Inzegane Ait Melloul and the province of Chtouka Ait Baha . However, we did not have enough information since they did not have archives or documents that can help us.

According to the interviews held with the officials concerned, we concluded that the number of associations established in the Agadir region is 11,942 associations, or 4467 for the prefecture of Agadir Ida Outanane, 994 for the prefecture of Inzegane Ait Melloul and 6481 for the province of Chtouka Ait Baha . These associations operate in different sectors, except that this number does not include all active associations, since there are certain people who found associations to benefit precisely from the allocated subsidies. However, these individuals do not continue their projects, according to the manager interviewed, this is mainly due to the absence of monitoring and also control.

In the following table, we find the different types of associations, as well as their fields of activity :

Table 4: Types of associations and their fields of activity in the Agadir region

<p>Cultural and social associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artistic cultural: music, theater, cinema... • Presentation of medical care, patient support, and awareness against deadly diseases (AIDS). • Education and training: Literacy, academic support, and creation of income-generating jobs • Social solidarity: care and integration of disabled and elderly people, and help for people in difficult situations • Social services: guarding and security, development of electricity, providing drinking water • other...
<p>Rights associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for civil rights and civil liberties. • Child protection. • Protection of ecology (Argan tree...).

<p>Religious associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of mosques. • Surveillance of ancient schools. • Maintenance of zawiyas, tombs and sanctuaries. • Religious and doctrinal trends.
<p>Sports associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • basketball , handball clubs ... • Martial arts clubs: taekwondo, karate, boxing, full-contact. • Water sports clubs: Windsurfing, sailing, water skiing. • Motor sports: such as motorcycles, bicycles, cars, planes, etc. • Hunting clubs...
<p>Scientific research associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations interested in scientific research and studies.
<p>Professional Affiliations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Affairs. • Organization of professional sectors.
<p>School associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations of parents and guardians of students. • School sports associations. • “Success school” support associations.
<p>Residential neighborhood associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations responsible for residential gatherings.
<p>Other Associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperatives Organization of festivals and major artistic exhibitions.

Source : The author

2. Mutuels

A mutual is a private non-profit company, which aims to help and provide assistance to state or private sector workers, in the field of health, while deducting contributions from their salaries.

Mutual societies are a fundamental source for social risk legislation. The proof is the large number of mutual societies that have recently been listed. The categories of these mutuals are: the general mutual of national education "MGEN" with the largest part, the mutual of the National Office of Railways "ONCF", the Mutuelle Agricole Marocaine D'Assurances "MAMDA", the mutual insurance company for fishermen and seafarers "IMINI"... etc. The Caisse Nationale des Organismes de Prévoyance "CNOPS" encompasses all of these mutuals. It has the role of coordinating activities to cover expenses relating to the health care of members.

The mutuals are distinguished by their role in the management of the AMO in relation to the civil servant in the State sector, and also to the mutualists who are identical to those advocated by the mutuals in France. In Morocco a mixed system has been installed. As with the administrative organization of the country, it was based on what pre-existed to reform it, and adapt it to the particularity of Moroccan society, which in addition to being a solid reform of health risk coverage, continues to develop a health component via the National Institute of Public Health.

The National Fund of Social Welfare Organizations presents the union of eight mutual societies from the public sector of Morocco. According to the CNOPS located in Agadir, we were able to count eight mutual societies, namely:

- The Police Mutual created in 1919;
- The Mutual of Customs and Indirect Taxes, created in 1928;
- The Mutuality Works of Civil Servants and Similar Agents of Morocco "OMFAM";
- The Post and Telecommunications Mutual, founded in 1946;
- The General Mutual Society of Public Administration Personnel of Morocco "MGPAPM", founded in 1946;
- The General Mutual of National Education of Morocco "MGEN", founded in 1963;
- The Mutual of Auxiliary Forces "MFA", founded in 1976;
- The Staff Mutual of the Port Operations Office "MODEP" in 1995.

As part of the proximity policy we find mutual societies which are delocalized, and having administrations at the level of the city of Agadir, which are:

The Police Mutual, the Mutual of Civil Servants and Similar Agents of Morocco, the Mutual of the Personnel of the Port Operations Office, the Mutual of Auxiliary Forces, and the General Mutual of National Education of Morocco.

It should be noted, at this level, that the rest of the mutual societies are centralized in the capital Rabat.

3. Cooperatives

The cooperative is the third component of social entrepreneurship, it will be treated as an example of social enterprises in a field of study which is the region of Agadir.

In the city of Agadir, we find the Cooperation Development Office which is an administration dependent on the Presidency of the Governmental Council. It provides cooperatives with training and information, and provides them with legal support.

It should be noted that this office does not only concern cooperatives operating in the Agadir Ida Outanane prefecture , but also the entire Souss Massa region.

According to ODCO, cooperatives have reached several stages in their historical evolution, namely:

- Stage of establishment of cooperatives by the authorities of the protectorate for economic and political reasons in 1937;
- Stage of State intervention in the management of cooperatives: 1956-1983, and the creation of ODCO: in this period the cooperatives experienced rapid growth, but the misuse of the subsidy killed the spirit of entrepreneurship and innovation among cooperators;
- In this stage the cooperatives are disengaged from the state, and also the uniqueness of the cooperative legislation in 1983: this policy forms an outline towards the creation of autonomous cooperatives, however they require significant efforts in terms of the valorization of the human element based on training and awareness;
- During this stage, cooperatives were used as an instrument for creating jobs, an instrument integrating women into working life, an instrument for organizing the informal sector, etc. This phase, which began in 2000, is characterized by the interest given to cooperatives by different donors, and

programs such as INDH, Maroc Vert, Ibhaz, MC, middle class habitat , etc.
».

Since we will work more precisely on the prefecture of Agadir Ida Outanane , the prefecture of Inzegane Ait Melloul and the province of Chtouka Ait Baha , we will present in the following table the distribution of cooperatives according to sector of activity.

Table 5: Distribution of cooperatives according to sector of activity

Activity area	Number of cooperatives operating in the Agadir region			
	Total	Agadir Ida Outanane	Inzegane Ait Melloul	Chtouka Ait Baha
Agriculture	347	106	40	201
Craftsmanship	88	37	26	25
Transportation	4	3	1	-
Trade	16	1	2	-
Consumption	3	-	14	2
Fishing	11	8	-	3
Services	9	9	-	-
Total	478	164	83	231

Source: ODCO, 2017

III. Relationship between sustainable development and social entrepreneurship

Coming from distinct currents within social movements, organizations and institutions, it quickly became apparent that the two notions overlap in several respects, first of all, they are based on similar principles, that is to say self-reliance, development centered on the satisfaction of needs, and democracy. Secondly, they propose alternative methods to satisfy social needs and finally they wonder deeply about the definition of collective social well-being, the common good, and in general the question concerning the general interest.

1. the relationship of social entrepreneurship towards sustainable development

It is through their alignment with the general interest, despite a distinct analysis of human activities and their particularly economic and social impact, that social entrepreneurship and sustainable development are especially linked. This point of view agrees with that of Gendron: "one cannot speak of a sustainable development that takes into account the environment, society and the economy at the same time without pointing out the need to see the economy differently, to rethink the relationship between the economic and the social. (...). Also, these two notions

take note of the inadequacies or biases that economic rationality justifies between social actors. They call for taking into account the human and social consequences or impacts of economic actions and their materialization.

1.1 The three stages of the emergence of sustainable development

The first phase is that of denunciation. During this stage, several international institutions collaborated extensively in making sustainable development more widespread, which aims to confront the problems affecting the environment by proposing solutions.

However, it must be noted that during this first stage, sustainable development constituted a project promoted by important international bodies, not yet materialized by the actors in question.

The second phase of dissemination of sustainable development concerns the creation of an institutional interpretative framework aimed at engaging a larger number of actors. It is a question of involving representative groups such as professional associations, regulatory agencies, unions in order to make a contribution to the dissemination of the process (Greenwood and Hinings 1996). Since the second half of the 1990s, these institutions have started to carry out the project. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, clarified that sustainable development is a concept that "comprises concerns of equity and social cohesion, in addition to the need to guard against risks that threaten the general goods of the humanity".

The third phase focuses on the implementation of procedures whose objective is the pragmatic involvement of the different economic actors, especially businesses, so that they take on a sustainable nature, while aiming for a conciliation between economic growth, environmental respect and social equity (Boutillier 2008). This phase is the most crucial step in the concrete dissemination of sustainable development practices.

The contribution of the various actors who are committed to the path of sustainability remains effective. This is reflected, as the European Union calls for corporate social responsibility, for which the term "social" has an environmental character as well as a societal character . A socially responsible company is one that acts responsibly by respecting the interests and expectations of all its stakeholders (Campbell 2007).

1.2 Social entrepreneurship, a lever for sustainable development

Research in entrepreneurship is not yet consistent enough to be the subject of conformity around this concept, studies which focus on social entrepreneurship, as being a type of entrepreneurship, also note the multiplicity of definitions, and confirm the absence of a unifying

paradigm in this field of research (Dees 1998) .

Advocating for sustainable development, which respects human rights and which encourages the rational use of resources, social entrepreneurship which aims to deal with the most complicated social problems, such as unemployment, precariousness, exclusion, poverty, and crimes... are all negative externalities generated by activities that are legitimate or illegitimate, and therefore requiring the proposal of innovative mechanisms (Johnson, 2000) . Social entrepreneurship, which aims to trigger social change by satisfying vital and necessary human needs in a sustainable way, could then be a founding lever of sustainable development.

1.3 Connection between social entrepreneurship and sustainable development

This articulation can be formalized, but depends on the definition chosen for one or the other concept. This choice is not without repercussions on the quality of the articulation. But it has a lot to gain from the acceptance of social entrepreneurship representative of a sphere, and of sustainable development understood in a broader way compared to that of the environmentalist vision. The articulation of the concepts of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development requires, beforehand, the distinction of several levels of analysis or observation.

In our opinion, there is a double level of observation of the links between sustainable development and social entrepreneurship : theory and representations on the one hand, and practices on the other. The distinction between these two levels has the advantage of avoiding an articulation marked by confusion.

1.3.1 Conceptual joints

Four types of joint can be identified :

- The environment and sustainable development as indicators of the socially constructed dimension of the economy ;
 - Social entrepreneurship and sustainable development sharing the social aainterface ;
 - Social entrepreneurship as an operationalization of sustainable development ;
 - Social entrepreneurship and sustainable development as mutual contributors.
- ✓ Environmental problems reveal the dysfunctions and inadequacy of the economic system. As an example, waste is an indicator of everything that is wrong with the economy. To succeed in transforming waste, we must rethink the ways of producing and consuming. This mission goes against traditional economic development. How to reconcile environment and economy? Ultimately, this mission will be in opposition to polluting companies that generate waste.

- ✓ In other words, environmental issues address the relevance of the empowerment of the economic sphere, with the idea that their resolution requires the participation of social actors. From now on, these questions must be reviewed from an economic, social, political and scientific angle. Which calls for a social construction of environmental problems by: on the one hand, the highlighting of social controversies inherent to ecological questions, for example water management, factory discharges, or waste management methods and, on the other hand, through the participation of representatives of industry circles, scientists, environmentalists and social groups, etc. Thus, environmental problems highlight the need to adopt a social perspective of the economy, as suggested by the theoretical perspective inherent in the social economy. It is precisely this social dimension which corresponds to the central point of the second articulation, between social entrepreneurship (social economy) and sustainable development formalized by the idea of interface.
- ✓ Social entrepreneurship and sustainable development : In this case, sustainable development and social entrepreneurship are concepts that do not overlap completely. In this respect, sustainable development is the result of the action of a set of extremely varied and different actors, as well as a process of change. Indeed, the social dimension of sustainable development comes from the social dimension of social entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, sustainable development also contains other dimensions (the environment and the economy) which do not necessarily integrate social entrepreneurship. Furthermore, social entrepreneurship has dimensions different from those of sustainable development. The challenge is then to specify the interface between the two.
- ✓ Social entrepreneurship as an operationalization of sustainable development : The third articulation is the one that has been taken up most often, and which poses social entrepreneurship as a means to achieve sustainable development. Confronted with each other, the notions of social entrepreneurship and sustainable development are articulated and hierarchical in such a way that sustainable development poses itself as an ideal of development, objective and result of activities (which involve several sectors such as that of the social economy) carried out in a particular mode (or even alternative) and above all voluntarily and collectively adopted; while social entrepreneurship would fall under operationalization. The latter's contribution would therefore be part of a more global system, carrying an ideal of development. Social entrepreneurship plays, in these conditions, a major and privileged role, in particular thanks to its values, oriented

towards the processes of socio-economic transformation , however the notion of sustainable development seems to us to represent an expression of the common good.

1.3.2 Field joints

The articulation between the actors of social entrepreneurship and those of sustainable development, which we link here to the “field” dimension of the articulation between the two fields seems affirmed to us . Organizations falling within the framework of social entrepreneurship are essential actors in sustainable development, because they are sometimes instigators of change, at the level of institutional, economic and social mobilization. In this regard, environmentalist groups and social entrepreneurship organizations with environmental aims can be cited as examples. Other examples relating to solidarity finance or tourism can also be mentioned.

This raises the question of the double “ Bottom Line”, that is to say the double basic requirement of social entrepreneurship organisations. Indeed, these must, like private companies, be concerned with profitability and financial performance, while meeting the objectives specific to companies entering into the framework of social entrepreneurship and the aim of sustainable development, such as the solving environmental problems and the primacy of people. In these circumstances, financial performance proves to be a real challenge, while management strategies become essential.

Social entrepreneurship at the ecological level presents a reform and also a revolution. Social entrepreneurship constitutes a reform, to the extent that several organizations countering the hegemonic neoliberal trends are involved, supported by small public programs. It is also a revolution, since social entrepreneurship in the environmental field offers a new way of doing things, and contributes to social innovation. In other words, social entrepreneurship is the materialization of new economic, social, cultural and political practices that can truly demonstrate how to implement new solidarities and alternatives, both at the local and global level.

CONCLUSION

We have underlined the obvious interrelation between social entrepreneurship and the dimensions of sustainable development, their convergences moving towards a logic of intra and intergenerational development marked by common complementary principles of equity, human and social development, bonds and solidarity. Obviously, these principles are a break with the principle of development based on economic growth alone.

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